

Narrative Approach (NA) and the Sociocultural Embeddedness of Social Work Practice in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper depending mainly on systematic review of extant literature and a case study examines the utility and relevance of the narrative approach to social work practice in Nigeria. It focused especially on how the approach facilitates the acceptance of the discipline as well as embodies consistency with extant sociocultural contexts. Even though the narrative approach is a novelty in the social work practice and intervention repertoire in Nigeria, it seems congruent with social cultural norms of storytelling and sharing of burdens through oral narratives. The paper pinpoints the probable challenges that would confront the utilization of the approach. It equally identifies opportunities ranging from the deepening of the scope of the discipline, empowering creativity, and initiatives of social workers, enabling bonding to improving the acceptability of the discipline among the people. It therefore advocates for the utilization of the narrative approach since the approach while not jettisoning formal theories and models provides opportunity for creativity and initiative-based practice that aligns with the sociocultural contexts shared by both the practitioner and the client.

Keywords: intervention, Africa, social workers, problems, theory

Introduction

The paper interrogates the utility and value of the narrative approach to social work practice in Nigeria focusing especially on how it enables the acceptance of the discipline as well as embodies consistency with extant sociocultural contexts in the Country. Without doubt, the narrative approach is a novelty in social work practice and intervention repertoire in Nigeria. Therefore, while the narrative approach is not entirely novel in social work practice or interventions globally (see, Riessman, 1993; Roscoe, et al, 2011; Milner, 2001; Riessman and Quiney, 2005; White, 2007 etc.), it is a method that has neither been widely adopted nor made common among the social work practice community in Nigeria. The above situation persists even though NA's greatest strength may cohere with its being situated in the cultural and social contexts of storytelling and sharing experiences that can be claimed by virtually all social groups in the world.

However, there is reason to believe that the above attributes of social life are perhaps much more ingrained in the African environment than any other part of the world. As a result, a method of social work practice or intervention based on these social attributes may achieve more acceptance than other formal and Western-inspired methods. But even more compelling of the utility of the NA in social work practice in Africa is the social legitimacy challenge which the discipline has faced in the continent where the duties or roles of the professional social workers are seen as better performed or achieved through primordial and age-old means ranging from the family to the kin group and network of friends. This challenge is acute in the case of Nigeria where despite nascent official recognition as a professional discipline, social workers face bewildering challenges of explaining their utility or roles in the society and even more daunting is justifying such roles and the usefulness of social work.

In view of the above, a social work orientation that is squarely located in the norms of brotherhood (epitomised through listening to each other's problems and offering advice) and seeming mutual sharing of problems may resonate with the culture of the people and provide invaluable opportunities for widening the social acceptance and scope of influence of the discipline. There is no gainsaying the fact that the relevance and perseverance of primordial linkages as sources of solving personal problems and crisis of the individual in the society have been gradually eroded by modernity. In such a context, the reliability of these links for the individual confronted with problems have declined over the years as urbanization, capitalism and its ethos of individualism and self-survival as well as intrusive formal regulations and increasing popularity of the nuclear family take their toll on

these primordial linkages especially the extended family and kin group as the bastions of the problem solving and coping capacity of people.

Against the obvious retreat of these primordial linkages, the need and relevance of social workers who serve as problem mediators cannot be overstressed. Despite the above observations, a good number of people in Nigeria are still either totally ignorant of the availability and relevance of social workers or are decidedly unclear about how social work can impact on their lives or their challenges (see, Anugwom, 2016). That social work battles acceptance or credibility problems in Nigeria should not sound strange. This appears a common issue with the discipline not only in developing countries but even beyond. Thus, social work battles credibility even in such a developed context as Singapore (see, Fareez and Mohan, 2018). Given the above ambivalence, the need for entrenching and popularising social work and its roles/functions in Nigeria cannot be overstated. Therefore, linking formal social work practice to approaches like the narrative therapy which straddles between formality and informality as well as anchored on the utility of personal narratives akin to the ones that were common in traditional social settings may not only improve the credibility of the discipline but increase its acceptability. Hence, the study explores the value of the narrative approach in social work practice in Nigeria and more critically pinpoints areas of intervention where the approach may be truly invaluable.

The What and How of Narrative Approach in Social Work

Narrative approach debuted in the 1980s and received its initial boost from the social constructivist and other relativist approaches in the social sciences. In this way, it emphasised the basic tenets of the above orientations that nothing significant exists outside language and events and gave preference to how individuals in society identify, order, and give meanings to events and phenomena in the society and more crucially how individual shape and reshape themselves and their world through stories. According to Reissman (2005:393), “narrative approach in the human sciences is a 20th century development; the field has ‘realist’, ‘postmodern’ and constructionist strands”. But the author goes on to point out that scholars are not generally agreed on the precise origins and even precise conceptualization of the approach and offers that it could be understood from differing perspectives [perhaps, in relation to the discipline concerned]. However, despite the above expected ambivalence among scholars, there is not much disagreement about the fact that the approach is motivated by the need to prioritise the experience of the individual.

Thus, Fredman and Combs (1996) are of the view that the goal of the narrative approach is to enable social workers engage with people [clients] to generate alternative stories or to thicken contradictions to the problem saturated stories [in their lives] in the bid to make them not support or lend credence to such problems. In a sense, it is the utilisation of stories not only to recount the past but more fundamentally to overcome or surmount the problems of the past and engender a healthier and more functional living for the client. In the narrative approach, therefore, the remit of the social worker is to unravel how the world is understood subjectively from the point of view of the client. Stories in this case become important because they are parts of the individual’s history and identity and provide some meaning to their lives and how they relate to things and other people around them. Given the centrality of stories which convey life episodes, changing or recreating stories are critical to enabling people to overcome problems, limitations and achieve closure over trauma. The above is captured in the sentiments, “therefore, the social worker here works with the service user to develop and encourage alternative constructions which make it possible to work in an empowering and anti-oppressive way by developing potential, rather than focusing upon problems” (Roscoe and Madoc, 2009:6).

In a popular sense, narrative approach is often seen as resembling what has been labelled, ‘talking about talk’ which involves discussing both what is palatable and what is not with the client during sessions (see, Fredman, 1997; Dallos, 2006).

The narrative approach can be viewed as clearly underscoring the perceived functions of social work as a peculiar discipline oriented towards the challenges and problems of the individual in the society. As the International Federation of Social Workers (2000:1) stated, “social work is a profession that promotes social change, problem-solving in human relationships and the empowerment and liberation of people to enhance well-being”. A conventional perception of the discipline as mediating in the everyday problems of individuals and families in the society. However, the call of the discipline apparently goes beyond this simple mandate. Thus, according to the Barclays Report (1982) in the UK, social workers are saddled with a second calling of interacting face-to-face with their clients. In the words of the report while social workers are expected to assess the needs of their clients and facilitate the provision of social care, their second duty is to provide “face to face

communication between clients and social workers, in which social workers are helping service users to tolerate, or to change, some aspect of themselves or of the world in which they are living” (Barclays Report, 1982:33 – 34). In other words, social workers are expected not only to commission the extension of social benefits to people but also to serve as providers of in-person interaction that enable the client to comprehend, assess and choose paths and services that respond to her situation in a collaborative manner. Thus, the narrative approach apart from providing the much-needed one-to-one communication enables the setting of the context in which fruitful and mutually respectful collaboration and resolution occurs between the social worker and the client.

Narrative approach requires four key attributes of the social worker. These are empathy, collaboration, loyalty, and trust (see, Patton, 2001; Springwood and King, 2001). These attributes are critical to engagement with the client. Narrative approach can be perceived also as constituted of both professional theorising and what is called lay theorising. Thus, “whereas professional theorising reflects the formal theories and methods of social work which social workers draw on in their everyday work, lay theorising consists of common-sense assumptions which reflect broader cultural and social ideas which contain discriminatory and oppressive assumption” (Roscoe et al, 2011:48). Thus, the approach challenges the prevalence of traditional and formal theories and practice models in social work. For instance, there is no gainsaying the prevalence of systems theory and psychodynamic theory in social work overtime (see, Scoufield and Pithouse, 2006; Bull and Shaw, 1992).

The narrative approach equally performs a critical function seen as advisable to social workers i.e. listening to the views of clients and service users. According to Roscoe et al (2011: 47), “narrative social work is defined as a conversation between theory and practice, which can lead to development in both social workers and service users”. This conversation occurs in a situation of equality, mutual respect, and cordiality between the practitioner and the client and in which gatekeeping tendencies are abhorred.

Narrative approach entails a new route to social work practice. There are many strategies or approaches to narrative therapy. However, the approach demands essentially a decentred approach in which the social worker adopts an attitude that depict respect, curiosity, and hopefulness (see, White 1997). These attitudes are critical in the venture to negotiate and interact with clients regarding the paths they want to take and in assuring them that they are the authors of their lives. In other words, the social worker rather than bossing or acting as the fountain of knowledge adopts the toga of a guide and position herself as an appreciative ally or friend (see, Madsen, 2003; 2014). The above generates both the trust of the client and effective collaboration. In effect, the social worker true to calling avoids value judgements and propensity towards pointing out wrong and right and rather assume respect for the client and his perceptive on issues. Being a guide thus demands a radical shift from being a gatekeeper or judge to being an ally and collaborator with the client in negotiating access to the service of help required.

The fact that social workers may generally be reluctant to adopt methods in practice that deviate from the orthodox notions of science and professionalism has been mentioned in the literature (see, Margolin, 1997; Riessman, 1993). This tendency which prevails even in the developed societies of the world can be related to the assumption that western scientific knowledge systems are the accepted norms of knowledge pursuit. So, the deviation from these systems which are the foundations of theory and practice in the entire social sciences would predictably breed both scepticism and rejection. The above problem is even more profound in the developing world where these disciplines and epistemologies underlining have been mere reproductions or mimicry of what obtains in the West.

The narrative approach embodies a combination of both reflexive and indexical accounts of episodes. It thus encompasses what happened, to whom it happened and where (location) it happened. In this case while reflexivity refers to the reality or experience, indexicality is concerned with the context that is articulated in the narrative. The context of course is both the social and spatial context of the experience or the reality, however, the social context is much more determining and informative of the episode. As has been argued, “narrative approaches in social work should not only reflect aspects of ‘reality’ but should also challenge taken-for-granted assumptions in practice, including ways of interpreting policy initiatives and practice models such as Care Management” (Roscoe, 2011:50).

Materials and methods

The study made use of desk review in gathering information for the paper. This entailed the desk review of cogent extant literature and documentary data on Narrative Approach. The review was guided by the thematic

analysis approach (Braun and Clark, 2006) and it focused on such themes as challenges to utilization of the Narrative Approach in social work practice in Nigeria, opportunities for fruitful Narrative Approach in Nigeria, and the case example of trial Narrative Approach in Nigeria. However, given the nature of Narrative Approach and its scope, the review included documents and materials that are extreme dated i.e. published before 1999. The systematic analysis of these materials provided information for the results and discussions in the paper. For the benefit of confidentiality, pseudo names were used in place of real names from the desk reviews.

Results and discussions:

Challenges to Utilization of the Narrative Approach in Social Work Practice in Nigeria

There are without question, some foreseeable and predictable challenges regarding the utilization of the narrative approach in social work practice in Nigeria. These challenges result mainly from the nature of the discipline (its epistemological bend) and the structural context of the Nigerian society. Some of these challenges which are discussed here include:

Peer Resistance: This is the resistance that would come from the community of social work professionals in Nigeria. This challenge would emanate mainly from the relative novelty of the narrative approach in Nigeria; the epistemological orientation of social workers; and the human predilection towards resisting change (see, Igbo and Anugwom, 2002). Therefore, getting colleagues to accept the approach and more crucially validate articles emanating from research or studies anchored on it may be difficult especially in the short run. However, the effectiveness and good reception of the approach by clients or service users over time may grant it reprieve from the above challenges. Social work colleagues have been trained in formal social work practice and curriculum oriented to Western scientific knowledge systems and the above may breed suspicion, resistance and even rejection of any approach that radically departs from dominant Western models (since the narrative approach is still of Western origin in relation to its usage in especially social work and psychology). Perhaps, the much-touted need for decolonization of knowledge (see, Anugwom, 2023) may as well embody the need to embed social work in the sociocultural context of its area of practice.

Incapacity in the Utilization of the Approach: Given the above scenario, it naturally follows that a lot of contemporary social workers in Nigeria lack the capacity, or skills needed for effective application of narrative approach in service delivery or intervention. There is no gainsaying the fact that the social work curriculum in Nigeria currently does not factor in narrative approach as an intervention model or general approach, thus utilising it may require that social workers take time to learn and get accustomed to how and where to utilise the approach in ways that fulfill the goal of intervention and social mediation. It is a loophole that can be easily and creatively overcome with commitment and desire to render useful service to clients.

Sensitive Nature of the Approach: While the approach suggests a simple and straight-forward method hinged on storytelling and sharing of experiences, its usage challenges the ability of social workers to recognise its inherent sensitivity. In other words, while engaged in narrative approach there is need to anticipate warning signs (signalling the opposite effects of the goals of the exercise), avoid recounting episodes that worsen the emotional frame of the client especially in cases of trauma; and side-stepping narratives that recreate acrimony and bile in the client or at least recreating them in ways that generate the opposite emotional response. Generally, the ability to do the above depends on the inter-personal and professional skills of the social worker. However, it is good to understand that people's emotional thresholds differ, and that the essence of the narrative approach is to enable clients to overcome traumatic and ugly incidents through retelling them and literally erasing them from their memories [check memory book] for relevant material/citation]. It is akin to the fact that memorialization enables people to overcome ugly or unpleasant incidents of the past and much more crucially achieve closure that enables them function productively as members of society (see, Anugwom, 2018).

Generally, social workers and other practitioners of the narrative approach may deal with sensitivity through focusing on the positives of the experience/encounter; utilization of repetition of pleasant episodes (for instance where clients showed strength of character; perseverance etc.). Equally helpful is the utilization of funny comments and anecdotes (not related to the episode) to lighten the mood and periodically re-charge the emotional energies of the clients.

Decisions on Strategy: This can be an issue in the situation of traumatic episodes/experience which occurred over time (like a long running war episode). In this case, while it is necessary to get the whole experience out of the client, there is need to arrive at strategies of going about the interaction. Even though the narrative approach

encourages the swapping of stories and exchanging of experiences between the social worker (even if indirectly using pronouns that make episodes and encounters not peculiarly about or limited to the client) and the client, the primary goal remains the story/experience of the client or service user. Therefore, such strategies would focus on timing of the narrative and periodization of the narrative (which comes first, the onset or the last episode; the worst experience or the experience that shows strength) as well as the venue/location of the interaction (to be determined by the client and gauging of her emotional strength by the social worker. For instance, some individuals cannot bear to revisit locations where they were abused or traumatised; while in others such visits are critical to overcoming the episode and healing from it) as well as the style/pattern of the interaction (however, an informal, camaraderie and empathetic style usually helps).

In other words, there are untold values in seeing each individual client as different from the others. Thus, it is the viewing of each client as unique that enables the social worker work with everyone to negotiate the best helping process or source of amelioration for the issue at hand (see, Duncan et al, 2004). Perhaps, the motto here should simply be that no two human beings are the same despite the broad commonalities generated by socio-structural contexts.

Choosing the Right Perspective: The narrative approach is helped greatly when the social worker adopts the so-called strength perspective which enables the process of collaboration and overcoming of the episode by the client in traumatic or unpleasant cases. The perspective enables focus on strengths and character stability of the client. This could follow the map offered by Ingamells and Epston (2012). These include skills, abilities, raw strengths and how these were utilised by the client. However, strengths should not be viewed wholly as personal characteristics but as intentional practices which are guided by the individual's values, dreams and hopes (Madsen, 2014). While the above sentence suggests some confusion, it simply refers to the fact that strengths in this case should not be considered as merely innate or inborn dispositions per se but rather character disposition brewed mainly by the values, hopes and dreams of the person concerned and not just something they were born with.

In addition to the above discussed challenges, one other criticism of the narrative approach is the assumed focus on the individual which may promote an individualistic and atomistic view of social phenomena. However, such criticisms often forego the fact that the individual apart from being member of a social group also functions within the normative parameters and institutional space in the society. Therefore, narratives are not solely about the experience of the individual but experience and episodes within and influenced by the social environment.

Thus, it is argued, "whilst agreeably, we recognise that narrative practice in social work does not 'fit' all practices and responses to human struggle and complexity, we also argue that discursive approaches within the framework of Care Management are indeed possible" (Roscoe et al, 2011:57).

Opportunities for Fruitful Narrative Approach in Nigeria

It is highly plausible that narrative approach can enable social workers to overcome the often-noticeable feeling of not having skills and abilities but being mainly mediators of bureaucracy and organizational change (see, Carey, 2007; Jones, 2001). The above feelings are probably most acute in the developing world where both the credibility and relevance of social work is still far from resolved. Therefore, the approach may open windows for the social workers to reassert their skills and display profound abilities.

Apart from its usage in addressing the challenges of clients or service users, the approach can also be used in field work supervision of students. In this situation, students can be encouraged to share and stimulate their fieldwork experiences and especially incidents that were particularly strange, unnerving, and challenging of what they have been taught and their expectations. In addition, the NA can be perceived as useful in de-officiating the contact between students on field work and their clients and making the field experience more exciting and allowable of both the creativity and initiating capacity of the students.

Equally important is to appreciate that the NA offers the scope for discipline of social work to overcome the strictures of being proceduralist and based on functional interventions without skill and creativity (see, Howe, 1996). In this case, social work given the challenges of a rapidly changing and technologies infused world needs to go beyond a purely managerialist orientation or existing mainly as what Harris (2008) termed a therapeutic enterprise. In the traditional sense, social work was basically embedded in a managerialist mode anchored on a realist conception of the world and deep respect or adoption of positivist and quantitative orientations to practice and even curriculum. In such a situation, social workers became mainly adept at rehashing and offering strictly

prescribed and formalised options and interventions. These were basically a strict by the book approach that stifled the creativity of the social workers and more critically was insensitive to the cultural context of practice and the sociocultural influences on clients. The narrative approach offers a new breath that seeks to overcome the above traditional strictures and limitations and more crucially envisions the client as a collaborative partner rather than a mere receiver of help or service from the state and its agencies through the intervention of the social worker.

Narrative approach equally encourages the deconstruction of the stories offered by the client and this is achieved through externalising conversations. The goal here is for the client to see the problems in new light and essentially as not the same as themselves. In other words, clients are made to perceive their problems and themselves as distinct and not the same. The act of deconstructing or externalising a problem thus enables the client to overcome the sense of failure or incapacity that is often generated by problems (see, White and Epston, 2005). There is no overstressing the fact that once the externalisation has been achieved the problems can be thoroughly examined and critiqued by the clients. In addition, externalising enables the promotion of the problem as not unique or limited to the individual and in the process beginning a therapeutic feeling of lack of failure or incapacity on the part of the client.

The narrative approach encourages or facilitates what has been described as a broader cultural and societal [social] ideas that embody a moral assessment of the client, which Hughes (1994) perceives as having a greater impact on social work practice than is recognised. In other words, the NA may build on the cultural norms and commonly shared ideas about both the episode and the proclivity of the client that impact on the process of engagement and effectiveness of intervention. The social worker does not therefore operate in a void or sheepishly stick to the normative guidance of extant theories and models but imbue broader cultural and societal notions that facilitate the resolution of the client's issues or problems.

Case Examples of Trial Narrative Approach in Nigeria – (desk review extracts from fieldwork reports – 2015 & 2018)

Case one: Mrs A cares for a paraplegic wheelchair bound son who is in his early 20s. Mrs A has been constrained in her capacity to play other roles in the family especially as a single mother with three other younger children. In addition, she cannot focus daily on her job as a clerk in a government bureaucracy as she comes home during break every workday to check on her son and change his diapers and clothes. While one of the other children stays as a provisional carer during school holidays and a teenage help that comes in otherwise during school periods, both people cannot and would not do diaper change and cannot take Rob (pseudo name) to the toilet (he would not agree, and they would rather not do it). Mrs A looks distressed, absent-minded and fretty outside of the house and hardly engages in any social activity. Engaging with her using the narrative approach revealed that she found words like 'stressed', 'over-worked', 'tired', and 'worn-out' as describing her daily activities especially regarding her family.

She also feels guilty and afraid about not doing enough for Rob and not taking adequate care of the other kids because of Rob. Interestingly, nobody outside there (outside her immediate family) seems to care about her situation. The social worker engaged Mrs A (who was referred by a welfare agency on the prodding of a student social worker that interacted briefly with the family during fieldwork practice) narratively over a six-week period; she gladly retold her daily chores of caring for Rob, her challenges and how she believed that if other people and the government cared, may be things could be better. At the end of the initial six weeks interaction, Mrs A confessed that she feels better knowing someone outside there cares, that there could be help outside if she reached out (the social worker introduced her to an NGO that runs an adult school for people who are physically challenged); and she overcame her feeling of guilt and fear because telling and retelling her story convinced her that she was doing her best within her context and other family pressures; and that she now looks forward to the now rescheduled monthly visits of social workers to discuss her problems and progress. While confessing her prior scant knowledge and unawareness of social work, she offered to mediate the intervention of social workers in other households in the community with different coping challenges. The social worker utilised a couple of personal stories of people in her own circles of friends and families who are also burdened by similar problems or challenges especially widows (externalising of the problem).

Case two: Mr B got married to his beautiful wife fifteen years ago and they agreed on having three children. Two years after the wedding, there was no pregnancy yet so they decided to go for medical check-up. There, it was revealed that though Mrs B was ok, Mr B was sterile due to an untreated sexually transmitted disease. The

doctor did say he could begin some form of treatment to see if it could be corrected and that he did. They lived through it, seemingly, a happy couple but deep down each was very frustrated. During a discussion between Mrs B and a social worker at a workshop on adoption and child welfare, Mrs B described her life as “meaningless, miserable and finished” and this made the worker curious.

Applying NA, it was revealed that she secretly wanted to have children all these years but did not know how to go about it. She had considered In Vitro Fertilization (IVF), surrogacy and even adoption but did not know how to raise it with her husband. When asked why, she said that she thought that that would be unkind and insensitive to her husband knowing that he had a challenge and she felt guilty for wanting something that he could not give her. However, she also confessed that she was very angry with her husband because he was the cause of their childlessness yet in all those fifteen years, his family had been frustrating her, assuming that she was barren but he never rose to her defence even once. When she confronted him on that, he said he was protecting his dignity as a man and as such did not want anyone to even suspect that he had a problem let alone knowing it. That hurt her and she had been carrying the grudge for a long time yet unable to talk to anyone about it. She also said that it was beginning to affect her mental health and her job because she keeps thinking of the fact that was not getting younger and a time would come when she would be too old to take care of a child and she did not want to die without a child!

The social worker encouraged her to have a heart-to-heart talk with her husband; explaining to her that there was nothing wrong with adoption or IVF and since she was not going to sleep with another man to get the child, she was not doing anything wrong to her husband. Mrs B had the discussion with her husband and in the process realized that he also had bottled up a lot of frustration and anger over the years because he felt that she had lost respect for him as a man because he could not get her pregnant. He also believed that she did not understand exactly how he felt about his condition. They both agreed to a bi-weekly session with the social worker for a period of two months.

During the sessions, the social worker cited a number of examples where IVF and adoption have put smiles on faces of couples especially in these modern times. After the sessions, Mrs B confessed that she felt relieved and ready to get a child through adoption without any feeling of guilt and Mr B confessed that he felt a lot better too knowing that his real measure as a human being is not based only on his ability to get a woman pregnant. He stated that from that point onwards, he was ready to stand up and defend his wife should his family rebel against the adoption.

In effect, adopting the ‘use of self, in practice to achieve results is often done in the profession (see, Reupert, 2007; Dewane, 2007). A cocktail of personal experiences, social work values and skills as well as cultural heritage and norms in engaging with service users or clients is always useful. Also, the social workers in the cases above used narrative as an equal and sharing of experiences or swapping stories exercise (see, Roscoe, et al, 2011) while actively deconstructing Mrs A’s daily challenges and Mrs B’s frustration/anger she had been carrying around for over ten years. At the end, re-authoring occurred with Mrs A’s belief that she is not alone in such social situations and more crucially not making her situation peculiar and thus enabling her to adopt a positive new ‘self’ and Mr & Mrs B coming to terms with their situation in love and unity, accepting that it was not enough to ruin their union and agreeing on a common solution.

While the above examples may not be totally emblematic of the full strength of the narrative approach, it shows how it could be utilised even within the social context of Nigeria. It is also a basic and rudimentary process of its usage that responds to the level of social and intellectual development of social work in the country. However, the author is not unaware of the fine and distinctive social constructivist and social realist elements of the narrative approach which endorses both the discursive nature of social realities and the role of the human agency. Be the above as it may, the cases in point show that, Mrs A’s feeling at the end of six weeks initial engagement of being free of guilt and shorn of fears and the reconciliation and agreement on adoption by Mr & Mrs B epitomise the popular adage that a problem shared is a problem solved!

The above cases notwithstanding, there is still a big dearth in literature, knowledge and practice of NA in Nigeria due to the novelty of the approach in this part of the world. If given more attention by practitioners and other stakeholders in Nigeria, NA would be a very good approach to use especially while dealing with individuals and families. Unfortunately, it is still very challenging for practitioners using it in Nigeria as a result of the dearth in literature, knowledge and practice of the approach in the country.

Conclusion

It is necessary to state here (especially in view of the challenges) that there are no hard and fast rules (though there are general guides) about the engagement with the client or service user. But it is useful to appreciate that no two clients are the same, so what works for one person may not work for the other. Hence, there is need for the social worker to be perceptive, read body language and show nimbleness in adapting the approach to both the context and the client concerned, Therefore, while narrative approach appears simple and inherently doable, it is a sensitive and tact-requiring approach. The inability of the social worker to properly utilise the approach can easily lead to a counterproductive exercise that worsens the situation of the client rather than provide mediation and enable coping.

In other words, the approach reflects the need for social workers to think outside the box. As has been pointed out social work practice is usually a mix between the common sense [perceptive ability] of the social worker and the implicit application of models and theories (see, Pithouse and Atkinson, 1988; Hall, et al, 1999; Riemann, 2005). The above persists even though there might be scepticism regarding the use of common sense in the understanding of human complexity in social work practice in general (see, Hall et al. 2006; Riemann, 2005; Scourfield and Pithouse, 2006).

The above does not amount to a belief that the approach is without significant challenges not only in Nigeria but even elsewhere in the world. But as has been stated with reference to the Singaporean scenario, “despite these challenges, we feel that there is space for narrative ideas to complement social work practice in these settings. This may be achieved through the worker adopting a position of ‘guide’ through which narrative practices including strength-based conversations and letter writing can add value to the work we do” (Fareez and Mohan, 2018:34). The narrative approach is much needed now that there is often apparent disjuncture between theories and what confronts the social worker in practice. In other words, “social work has become increasingly more complex and some theories, in reality, may not be possible to apply in practice” (Roscoe, et al, 2011:49).

Modern day effective narrative approach may be better served through the democratic model advocated by Roscoe et al (2011). Here, narrative approach embodies three phases or stages of practice viz. engagement with the client; exploring and deconstructing stories (listening, capturing background assumptions, power relations and the culture history underpinning them) that may be perceived as theoretically and conceptually saturated [overbearing and burdensome]; and collaborating with clients to re-author [literally re-write] the stories. However, the stage of re-authoring is very crucial in social work practice especially among victims of abuse and other traumatic experiences or episodes. Re-authoring underlines overcoming and re-precepting the episode in ways that enable not only healing but closure and positive attitude to life. It equally entails a fresh understanding of the episode which facilitates self-development or the capacity to go forward.

Just like any other intervention or social work model, the narrative approach requires that the social worker thoroughly examine the likely usefulness of the method in any situation. In other words, an all size fits all mentality should be discarded and let the situation demand the suitability or otherwise of the narrative approach. After all, the narrative approach is one more approach in the tool kit of the professional social worker in Africa and elsewhere in the world. However, the above does not disown the amenability of the narrative approach to the cultural context of Africa where storytelling and sharing burdens are commonly perceived as critical to overcoming such experiences and healing.

Given the above, one agrees largely with the contention that, “all social work involves professional judgements and that narratives can give social workers opportunity to think about their own theory and practice and produce more thoughtful judgements”. In effect, the narrative approach while not jettisoning formal theories and practice models provides opportunity for creativity and initiative-based practice which more crucially aligns with the sociocultural contexts shared by both the practitioner and the client in most cases.

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